

SIGNIFICANCE OF DAMAGE CAUSED BY FATIGUE ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Andreas T. Echtermeyer¹, Leif Buene¹,
Bjørn Engh² and Odd E. Sund²

Det norske Veritas

¹A.S Veritas Research

²Det norske Veritas Classification A/S.
N-1322 Høvik
NORWAY

ABSTRACT

Fatigue of composites causes a loss of stiffness and development of damage before ultimate failure. A comprehensive study was undertaken to characterize these effects for five different (polyester and vinylester) resins reinforced by five layers of woven roving/chopped strand combination glass mat. Such laminates are typically used in marine applications like high speed craft.

S-N curves were obtained for all laminates. In addition, stress vs. strain curves were measured continuously under reverse loading ($R=-1$) up to 10^6 cycles. Analysis of these curves allows further insight in the fatigue process. Tensile moduli drop dramatically (25%) with increasing cycle number, but remain fairly constant in the compressive region. This behavior can be explained by effects of matrix cracking. It also indicates the need to define different moduli for nonlinear stress-strain curves. Absorbed energy (damping) can also be determined from the stress-strain curve and can be used as an indicator of the onset of rapid degradation of the material leading to ultimate failure. All data are compared for the five different resins, indicating the influence of resin properties on fatigue laminate properties.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Fatigue; Modulus/Stiffness; Damage; Woven Rovings.

1. INTRODUCTION

This study investigated laminates made from five different resins reinforced by a glass fiber combination of woven roving and chopped strand mat. These laminates are typically used in marine applications. A special emphasis will be put on stiffness loss during fatigue. Stiffness is not only an important engineering parameter, but can also be seen as an indicator of damage. Matrix cracking has been identified to cause stiffness reduction in static and fatigue tests [1-3]. Stiffness can be monitored continuously during an experiment allowing damage development to be studied. This development can give some more insight into the fatigue process, helping to understand the effects of different resins on fatigue properties.

Figure 1. Schematic of experimental setup for tension and compression tests.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Five different laminates were tested. All had the same glass fiber reinforcement : 5 layers of Rovimat 800/100 from Chomarat. This is a combination of a woven roving of 800 g/m^2 and chopped strand mat of 100 g/m^2 . The woven roving had the same amount of fibers in the weft and warp direction. Fibers were oriented in the 0/90 direction during testing, i.e. running in the load direction and perpendicular to it.

Five resins from Jotun Polymer were used to make the different laminates. An isophthalic polyester, a Neopentyl Glycol/iso polyester, a vinyl ester, a rubber modified vinyl ester, and an orthophthalic polyester. The laminates got the code numbers 1 to 5. Laminates were manufactured by hand layup and cured at 363 K (90°C) for 120 minutes.

All tests were performed on a servo-hydraulic MTS testing machine. Specimens were cut as straight $25 \times 5 \times 270 \text{ mm}$ coupons from the laminate, according to ISO 3268. In order to prevent buckling in compression an antibuckling device similar to the support jig of ASTM 695 was used. Dimensions of the device had to be slightly changed to a length of 140 mm and width of 25 mm to fit the specimens (there is no standard procedure for GRP tension-compression fatigue tests). A schematic of the experimental setup is shown in Figure 1. The gap between the antibuckling device and the grips was kept as small as possible (less than 2 mm). Strains were measured with an MTS Model 632.12C-20 extensometer, attached to the edge of the specimen. Stress-strain curves could be taken continuously by a computerized data acquisition system.

Laminate Number		1	2	3	4	5
Primary Tens. Mod.	E_I GPa	17.1 ± 0.4	16.1 ± 0.4	16.8 ± 0.5	16.9 ± 0.7	17.3 ± 0.7
Second. Tens. Mod.	E_{II} GPa	12.1 ± 0.5	11.0 ± 0.7	11.4 ± 0.1	12.7 ± 0.6	11.5 ± 0.8
Compr. Modulus	E_C GPa	17.5 ± 0.5	16.5 ± 0.4	16.6 ± 0.3	15.9 ± 0.1	17.5 ± 0.2
Knee-Point Stress	σ_{sk} MPa	83 ± 5	88 ± 3	107 ± 7	106 ± 3	70 ± 5
Knee-Point Strain	ϵ_{sk} %	0.48 ± 0.03	0.54 ± 0.03	0.64 ± 0.04	0.63 ± 0.06	0.40 ± 0.05
Ult. Tens. Strength	MPa	209 ± 20	205 ± 6	227 ± 5	237 ± 14	226 ± 7
Tens. Strain at Fail.	%	1.4 ± 0.2	1.62 ± 0.12	1.72 ± 0.03	1.68 ± 0.07	1.77 ± 0.1
Ult. Comp. Strength	MPa	209 ± 9	258 ± 14	288 ± 25	259 ± 14	294 ± 23

Table 1 : Static Properties of Laminates

3. STRESS-STRAIN CURVES

3.1 Static curves Quasi static properties of all laminates were measured in tension and compression. Testing rates were 2 mm/min for both cases. Tensile stress-strain curves of all laminates show two linear parts separated by a static knee point. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the tensile stress-strain curve. Primary tensile moduli E_I , secondary moduli E_{II} , static knee-point positions and ultimate properties are listed in Table 1 for all laminates. Knee point positions are calculated from the intercept of the two lines fitting the primary and secondary part of the tensile curve. (Nonlinearity of the stress-strain curve starts at slightly lower stresses than the knee point stresses defined above.) Compressive tests show a fairly linear stress-strain curve up to the point of failure. Compressive properties are also listed in Table 1. Primary stiffness E_I of all laminates is fairly similar. Differences between the laminates can be seen in the knee point position. The two vinyl esters (laminates 3 and 4) show the highest values here, meaning the latest onset of damage.

Figure 2. Exaggerated schematic of a nonlinear stress-strain curve at first tensile loading and unloading for static and fatigue tests (not actual data points). Slopes of the stress-strain curve define a primary modulus E_I and a secondary modulus E_{II} . Unloading and second fatigue loading follow nearly the same curve, described by the initial fatigue modulus E_{fi} . The tensile fatigue modulus E_f drops with increasing cycle numbers to lower values.

3.2 Fatigue curves Fatigue tests were performed under reverse loading ($R=-1$), because it was found to cause most severe fatigue conditions in other composites [4]. Frequencies of the tests were varied between 2 and 5 Hz to keep the average load rate constant, avoiding viscoelastic effects. Low frequencies were chosen to prevent the specimens from heating up.

Stresses and strains were monitored continuously for all specimens. A typical sequence of stress-strain curves during fatigue is shown in Figure 3. The curve follows the static curve at first loading. First damage is introduced to the laminate when the static knee point stress is passed. This is reflected in a reduced slope of the stress-strain curve, like in a quasi static test. Unloading, however, does not follow the static curve anymore. The unloading curve is the secant line from the maximum stress and strain back to 0. This unloading line is also shown schematically in Figure 2. Permanent strains at 0 stress were found to be very small.

Continuing in the fatigue cycle to compressive loading, the slope of the stress-strain curve increases to the value of the static curve again. However, some compressive stress has to be applied before the original static compressive stiffness is regained. This pressure seems to close the cracks in the material. This means that the damage introduced to the specimen during the tensile part of the fatigue cycle does not influence the compressive modulus of the material. Once these cracks are closed under compression, the material appears undamaged to a stress-strain measurement.

Figure 3. Change of stress-strain curve during fatigue. Some of the 300 data points of each curve are enlarged to differentiate curves belonging to different cycle numbers. Loading and unloading curves are slightly separated by a hysteresis loop.

Compressive unloading follows closely the previous loading curve. Once the compressive stresses are getting too low to keep the cracks in the specimen closed, the slope of the stress-strain curve drops to the level in the tensile region. The next fatigue cycle begins with the tensile loading part. The curve nearly follows the unloading curve of the previous cycle, but the slope is slightly lower, indicating an increase in damage. The slope of the tensile part of the curve drops further with increasing cycle numbers, while the slope of the compressive part of the curve remains fairly constant up to a point shortly before ultimate failure. More details about the change of fatigue stress-strain curves can be found in another report [5].

4. FATIGUE STIFFNESS

Since the fatigue stress-strain curve is characterized by a fairly linear tensile and compressive curve, separated by the fatigue knee point, it can be described by a tensile fatigue modulus E_f and a compressive fatigue modulus E_{fC} defined by the respective slope of the stress-strain curve. The fatigue knee-point moves slightly into the compressive region during the first 20 to 100 cycles and remains at a constant stress level for the remaining part of the fatigue life.

Therefore, the compressive stresses required to close cracks causing an unchanged compressive modulus measurement do not change. The slight hysteresis effect apparent in the stress-strain curve has very little influence on the modulus definition [5]. It can be seen from Figure 3 that a single Young's modulus cannot characterize these materials. A fatigue secant modulus, for example, defined by maximum and minimum stress and strain, would always be lower than the compressive modulus E_{fC} and higher than the tensile modulus E_f .

Changes of the tensile fatigue moduli E_f with cycle number are shown in Figure 4 for laminate 2 as an example. The upper curve in Figure 4 shows data at a stress amplitude below the static knee point. Its character is slightly different from the other curves and will be described later.

4.1 Fatigue Stiffness above static knee point Tensile modulus curves of specimens cycled at stress amplitudes exceeding the static knee point stress are characterized by three features, as can be seen in Figure 4 :

1. The initial tensile fatigue modulus (of cycle 2) depends on the stress amplitude.
2. A period of slow modulus drop is characteristic for most of the fatigue life.
3. Once a critical modulus value is reached, stiffness drops rapidly and the specimen will fail after a few more cycles.

These are further explained in the following parts:

1. The initial tensile fatigue modulus E_{fi} can be calculated from the static stress strain curve. Stress and strain follow the static stress strain curve during first

Figure 4. Change of tensile fatigue modulus E_f with cycle number for various stress amplitudes of laminate 2. The upper curve shows data for a specimen cycled at a maximum stress below the static knee point stress of 88 MPa.

loading. However, at unloading they do not follow the static curve back, but go straight down to 0 stress and strain. (Only a negligible permanent strain develops during this first half cycle.) This line will be followed again during tensile loading and unloading of cycle 2. This sequence was described above and is also shown in Figures 2 and 3. The initial fatigue modulus E_{fi} (of cycle 2) is therefore given by the secant of the static stress-strain curve between the maximum stress σ_{max} and 0 stress. E_{fi} can be calculated for each fatigue stress amplitude by :

$$\begin{aligned} E_{fi} &= \sigma_{max} E_{II} / (\sigma_{max} - S_{II}) && \text{for } \sigma_{max} > \sigma_{sk} \\ E_{fi} &= E_I && \text{for } \sigma_{max} \leq \sigma_{sk} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

and $S_{II} = \sigma_{sk} - E_{II} \epsilon_{sk}$

where E_I is the primary and E_{II} the secondary modulus of the static stress-strain curve. S_{II} is the intercept of the secondary part of the stress-strain curve with the stress axis (see Figure 2). σ_{sk} and ϵ_{sk} are the stress and strain at the static knee point respectively. All values are listed for each laminate in Table 1. As the applied stress rises above the static knee point stress, damage gets inflicted on the specimen during first loading. This damage will increase with increasing stress levels σ_{max} , causing the initial fatigue modulus to drop further.

2. The period of slow modulus drop is characterized by a linear drop of modulus E_f with the logarithm of the cycle number if the specimen is cycled at stress amplitudes exceeding the static knee point stress. Stiffness drop rates, α , for all laminates are listed in Table 2. Drop rates vary from 0.6 GPa to 1 GPa per decade of cycles. The tensile fatigue modulus E_f is therefore related to the cycle number N by:

$$E_f = E_{fi} - \alpha \log N \quad \text{for } \sigma > \sigma_{sk} \quad (2)$$

where E_{fi} is the stress amplitude dependent initial fatigue modulus from Equation 1 and α is the modulus drop rate. Since a linear relationship between modulus drop and matrix crack density was found in other composites [2], matrix crack density seems to accumulate linearly with the logarithm of the cycle number in these woven roving laminates. Initial microscopic analysis on one laminate seems to confirm this, but more partially loaded specimens will have to be investigated. In addition, some specimens were cycled at fatigue stress amplitudes of an expected lifetime of 10^6 cycles, but tests were stopped after 10000 cycles and the residual strength was measured. The strength was the same as for unfatigued specimens for all laminates. Therefore, the damage that causes the tensile modulus to drop does not effect the strength of the specimens. One would expect that matrix cracks would not effect the strength of woven roving materials to a large extent.

Laminate Number		1	2	3	4	5
Modulus Droprate per Decade of Cycles	α GPa	0.80±0.08	0.68±0.04	0.85±0.11	0.99±0.06	0.60±0.17
Critical Fat. Modulus	E_{crit} GPa	13.4±0.6	12.4±0.4	12.8±0.3	12.7±0.3	13.3±0.3
Tensile Modul. Drop*	%	21	23	24	25	23

* E_{crit}/E_I

Table 2 : Fatigue Properties of Laminates

Figure 5. Primary static tensile modulus E_1 and critical fatigue modulus E_{crit} of the five laminates. The tensile fatigue modulus E_f drops gradually to the critical modulus E_{crit} during fatigue.

Figure 6. Change of damping during fatigue in laminate 2. All specimens were cycled to failure, except the one cycled at a maximum stress of 52 MPa.

3. Once the tensile modulus E_f has dropped slowly to a critical value E_{crit} , rapid drop sets in. Rapid drop in tensile stiffness coincides with rapid drop of compressive stiffness E_{fc} , which stayed constant at the static value E_c before. A different damage mechanism, probably damage of the load bearing fibers, seems to get activated and causes ultimate failure soon. This critical fatigue modulus appears to be independent of the stress amplitude. Critical tensile fatigue stiffness values, E_{crit} , for all laminates are shown in Figure 5 and listed in Table 2. They are 20-25% below the initial static stiffness. This drop should be

considered when using these composites in structures exposed to cyclic loading. At cycle numbers beyond the critical modulus the material gets very soft and degrades rapidly.

Another indication of severe damage formation is an increase in damping after the critical modulus is reached. Figure 6 shows damping vs. cycle numbers at various stress amplitudes. Damping is here defined as the absorbed hysteresis energy divided by the average mechanical work per fatigue cycle. Damping stays constant during the phase of slow modulus drop. This means that the accumulation of damage causing the tensile modulus to drop does not influence damping. However, damping appears to be slightly higher at higher stress amplitudes. Once the stiffness has dropped to the critical modulus and rapid degradation of the specimen sets in, damping increases too, i.e. more energy is absorbed in the specimen. Therefore, damping may be an indicator of damage reducing the strength of the specimen. However, the quick rise of the damping approaching the end of the fatigue life will give very short warning before failure. The specimen cycled at the highest fatigue stress shows a continuous increase in damping, which may indicate severe damage formation over its entire, but short, lifetime of 205 cycles.

4.2 Fatigue stiffness below the static knee point Specimens cycled at stress amplitudes below the static knee-point show slightly different fatigue behavior. The upper curve in Figure 4 shows stiffness changes for this case. The initial fatigue modulus E_{fi} (at cycle 2) is the same as the primary static modulus E_f . This would be expected, because the secant modulus is the same as the static loading modulus in the linear regime (see also equation 1). The tensile fatigue modulus E_f does not drop instantly with increasing cycle numbers, but has an initiation period of a constant tensile stiffness preceding the stiffness drop. This initiation period seems to increase if a specimen is cycled at very low amplitudes, i.e. far below the static knee point. However, only a few specimens were cycled at stress amplitudes below the static knee point, because their lifetime by far exceeds 1 million cycles, the testing limit for this study. Tests beyond 1 million cycles would be required to explore this point further.

After the linear drop of stiffness E_f with the logarithm of cycle number the reduction slows down. Stiffness stays eventually constant until rapid reduction at fatigue failure. This constant stiffness indicates a saturation of the damage. The modulus at saturation is slightly above the critical modulus E_{crit} . Damage saturation was also found in crossplied $[0/90_3]_S$ GRP [2,6]. It means that all matrix cracks have formed, but the laminate is able to sustain the damage. Most load will be just carried by the 0° fibers (of the woven roving) and the damaged parts are unloaded. Other composites dominated by 0° fibers also do not seem to lose much stiffness during fatigue. For example, $[0^\circ]$ laminates made from Carbon [7] and Kevlar [8] fibers show no drop in tensile stiffness before ultimate failure. Fiber dominated fatigue is also reflected in the S-N curve for small fatigue stresses (high cycle numbers). S-N curves of the five laminates are shown in Figure 7. At around 1 million cycles all curves meet at the same stress level, showing the same properties for all laminates in the state of matrix damage saturation.

5. S-N curves

Fatigue failure will be influenced by fatigue of the glass bundles and stress concentrations and stress transfer created by matrix cracking. Glass fiber bundles were found to lose 10% of their strength per decade of cycles under tensile fatigue [9]. Stress concentrations caused by other damage around the bundles can only increase this value. Figure 7 shows S-N curves of the five

Figure 7. S-N curves of the five laminates

laminates. Differences in fatigue behavior can be seen at low cycles numbers, while curves meet at high cycle numbers.

Fatigue at stresses above the static knee point (short life times) is influenced by matrix properties. The Neopentyl Glycol/iso polyester and the two vinylesters (laminates 2, 3, and 4) show a bit longer fatigue life at a given stress amplitude than the isophthalic and orthophthalic polyesters (laminates 1 and 5). The tensile stiffness loss during fatigue may give some insight into the different fatigue performance. First damage is introduced to the material at first loading already, causing stiffness to drop to the initial fatigue modulus. This damage develops gradually causing the stiffness to drop further by the modulus drop rate \propto listed in Table 2 until the critical stiffness is reached. Therefore, if the initial damage is low and the modulus drop rate is low, the fatigue life will be long.

However, if the material is cycled at fatigue amplitudes below the static knee point, all laminates have about the same lifetime. Matrix properties are not important anymore, because the matrix is in a state of damage saturation (see above). Fiber properties are controlling fatigue response at low stress amplitudes. All improvements obtained from better matrix properties are lost in the state of damage saturation. At 10^6 cycles fatigue strength is reduced to 80 MPa for all five laminates. Therefore, the average strength loss rate over the first million cycles relative to the static strength is between 10.2 % and 12 % per decade of cycles for the laminates. Laminates with the highest static strength have the highest average loss rate up to 10^6 cycles.

At higher cycle numbers, strength loss may approach 10% per decade which was observed for glass fiber bundles. There may also be a fatigue stress level so low, that matrix cracks will not develop anymore. However, more high cycle fatigue experiments would be required to determine properties at lower stress amplitudes resulting in very high cycle numbers.

6. CONCLUSIONS

- The main influence of the matrix on static properties of woven roving/chopped strand mat GRP is on the position of the static knee point. The

static knee point indicates onset of matrix cracking.

- The position of the static knee point plays an important role in the fatigue behavior of the laminate. The point determines the shape of the stress strain curve, which in turn determines the initial fatigue stiffness (at cycle 2). The knee point also separates different damage development patterns during fatigue.
- Fatigue stress-strain curves can be described by two linear parts separated by a fatigue knee-point. The two slopes of the curve are the tensile and compressive stiffness.
- Compressive stiffness does not change during fatigue (only drops just before final failure). Matrix cracks get closed under compression. The fatigue knee point is located at the stress required to close these cracks.
- Specimens cycled at stress amplitudes above the static knee point lose tensile stiffness in a slow fashion linearly with the logarithm of the cycle number. Stiffness drops at a low rate until a critical value is reached. Matrix cracking seems responsible for this stiffness loss.
- Specimens cycled at stress amplitudes below the static knee point show an initiation period before the tensile stiffness drops. After a slow linear drop with log cycle number stiffness reduction becomes less and eventually stops. A damage saturation state is reached. Further fatigue properties will be fiber dominated.
- Once fatigue stiffness has dropped gradually to a critical value, a new damage mechanism sets in leading to rapid stiffness reduction and ultimate failure. The critical stiffness is 20% to 25% lower than the primary static tensile stiffness.
- The matrix has an influence on low cycle (high stress) fatigue. But at lower stresses, (around the static knee-point stress) fatigue properties seem fiber dominated.

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8. REFERENCES

- 1 L.J. Broutman and S. Sahu, Proc. 24th Ann. Techn. Conf., SPI, Section 11-D, 1969 p.1
- 2 A.L. Hinghsmith and K.L. Reifsnider Damage in Composite Materials, ASTM STP 775, ASTM, 1982 pp 103-117
- 3 S.L. Ogin, P.A. Smith, P.W.R., Beaumont, Composites Science and Technology, 22, 23-31 (1985)
- 4 D. Schuetz, J.J. Gerharz, E. Alschweig, Fatigue of Fibrous Composite Materials, ASTM STP 723, ASTM, 1981 pp. 31-47
- 5 A.T. Echtermeyer, L. Buene, " Tensile and Compressive Stiffness Loss during Fatigue in GRP" to be published
- 6 M.G. Bader, L. Boniface, Fifth International Conference on Composite Materials ICCM-V, San Diego, Cal. , 1985, pp. 221-232
- 7 E.T. Camponeschi and W.W. Stinchcomb, Composite Materials: Testing and Design, ASTM STP 787, ASTM, 1982, pp. 225-246
- 8 H.L. Ganczakowski, M.F. Ashby, P.W.R. Beaumont, P.A. Smith, Composites Science and Technology, 37, 371-392 (1990)
- 9 J.F. Mandell, D.D. Huang, F.J. McGarry, Composites Technology Review, 3, 93 (1981)